

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CONCEPTS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND POSSIBILITIES OF ITS APPLICATION IN KAZAKHSTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878308>

Abstract

This article discusses the basic concepts of the circular economy. The principles and characteristics of its development are researched on the examples of other countries of the world. It has been established that in Kazakhstan the transition to a circular economy is at the initial level and has the possibility of its development in priority sectors of the economy, determined by legal norms.

Keywords: Circular economy, natural resources, environment, recycling, reuse.

The modern period of development of the world economy is characterized by both accelerated and unstable trends, which are also explained by such an important circumstance that in recent decades more and more different kinds of natural resources, energy and materials have been produced and used, and the problems of ensuring the preservation of the environment are becoming more and more important factors, provided that they directly affect the conditions for further social development. The world economy and the world community are facing global requirements, which are manifested every year more and more systematically, as they are in need of a comprehensive solution. According to a number of international funds, the current global crisis is long and very deep, as it affects all countries of the world and not only sectors of the economy, but also the living conditions of people on the planet. The indicators of the stability of the world economy are negatively affected by the environmental and social directions of its development. It should also be noted that the natural reserves of our planet and each state individually are being depleted as a result of the increased consumption of available resources. This approach also leads to climate change on the planet, to environmental problems associated with environmental pollution. The following conditions oppose this situation: the optimization of production, which makes it possible to prevent the depletion of available natural resources, as well as modern economic concepts, which are trends such as the system of conscious consumption and the circular economy.

Based on this, it should be emphasized that the above reasons indicate the importance of implementing in all countries the concept of a circular economy, which is beginning to gain more importance all over the world, since the traditional economy, known as the linear economy, cannot solve all the problems of modern sustainable development. The world community, requiring simultaneous integrated development, expressed in the following:

- 1) sustainable economic growth;
- 2) ensuring environmental protection;
- 3) ensuring public welfare.

A similar situation is noted in Kazakhstan, which is part of the world economy, and it requires its correct solution. In the current situation, it is essential to find scientific economic approaches that allow the formation of more efficient economic systems, characterized by a high level of sustainability and created on the principles of a careful and reasonable attitude to the environment and resource conservation. Based on this, in the course of this study, the importance of studying the concepts of a circular economy, the economic factors of its development in modern conditions, based on scientific findings and practical results in this area, is determined. And it is also necessary to consider the indicators of its development in Kazakhstan and develop recommendations for their use in our republic. At the same time, special attention is paid to issues that show how, in the conditions of the modern development of the Kazakhstani economy, it is most effective to promote the principles of the circular economy, in which areas it is necessary to focus special attention and whose world experience can be adopted.

At the first stage, we considered the basic concepts of the circular economy.

A circular economy (or cyclical) is an economic phenomenon, according to which consumption and production take place in a certain closed cycle. Within this cycle, three conditions must be taken into account:

- 1) maximum use of resources;
- 2) no accumulation of waste;
- 3) no negative impact on nature [1].

The circular economy is opposed to the classical linear economy, which operates according to the following principle: take, make, dispose ("create, use, destroy waste") [1]. The concept of the circular economy is based simultaneously on the achievements of two scientific branches: economics and ecology. The concept

is based on the assumption that only alternative methods of production can compensate for the negative impact of production and consumption on the environment.

The circular economy as a concept appeared for the first time in the 60s of the twentieth century. Its first definition was proposed in 1966 by Kenneth Boulding, an economist from the United States. According to the author, the economy and the environment require interaction and must develop harmoniously and in a certain balance. His definition of a circular economy is based on harmonious interaction [2].

It should be noted that the conceptual concept and content of the circular economy began to be explored and discussed since the late 60s of the twentieth century. However, to date, the concept itself is still developing and enriched with new approaches. Let us show how the idea of a circular economy was revealed, supplemented and changed in the scientific community, using some examples. In the 70s of the last century, it was started talking about the circular economy relatively actively, mainly in individual European countries; there they began to offer a circular model of the economy to replace the industrial model, which directly depended on the active use of raw materials.

In 1970, Pearce and Turner considered the two-sided influence of natural resources on the economy, since they affect economic systems and determine their efficiency and development [4]. In 1989, it is noted that the traditional or linear economy (David Pearce and R. Kerry Turner) does not take into account the recycling of waste, which has created conditions according to which the environment becomes simply a repository for waste. Their concept of a circular economy is based on the analysis of the influence of natural cyclical mechanisms, including the environment [3].

The concept of cradle-to-cradle zero-waste production (McDonough and Braungart, 2002) is based on the need to develop and implement an independent certification system that is designed to assess the safety of products based on the production materials and technologies used in their creation. This concept is based on the certification of non-waste production, which allows to promote certified products [4]. The concept of systemic change (Preston, 2012) is based on collaboration

along the entire customer value chain between all or different participants. This is due to the fact that the introduction of a circular economy involves systemic changes [4]. The concept of a circular economy (European Commission 2014), according to which production should be transformed into a new industrial model that can support the transition of industrial production to a different economic model. According to this concept, the circular economy is based on the principle of creating such a closed system in which the economy and the environment are related [4]. The concept of the circular economy is based on the fact that it is possible to ensure economic growth regardless of the extraction of natural resources. It is also based on the possibility of forcing resources through the continuous use of materials (Persson, 2015), which can, regardless of the extraction of resources, only through their processing and reuse, affect economic growth [4]. The concept of a circular economy as an economic system implies a complete change in the scientific paradigm (Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2018). According to this concept, the definition and principles of the circular economy are formed, based on a review of existing concepts and systematic research on this topic [4].

This allows us to stop at the definition of the circular economy, given in 2018 by Prieto-Sandoval et al., as an economic system that acts as a paradigm shift, according to which human society and nature are interconnected and human activities are aimed at preventing environmental pollution, depletion of resources, ensure the reduction of resource and energy dependence. The circular economy promotes general and private sustainable development through the introduction of new principles at the micro level (consumer and enterprises), meso level (symbiosis of economically integrated agents) and macro level (city, regions and states). According to the authors, in order to achieve a cyclical model of the economy, systemic ecological innovations of a restoring plan and the adoption by society of new laws of production and consumption are required [4]. This definition, in our opinion, is the most complete and fully reflects the most important elements and aspects that characterize the circular economy. The circular economy is determined by the main principles reflected in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Principles of the Circular Economy [5]

The circular economy is also based on the implementation of the 4R principle, which provides circular value chains: reuse, recovery, recycle, reduce (reduction in resource consumption in production). In a circular economy (hereinafter, CE can be used) there is a

closed supply chain, which, as its main factor, involves both direct and re-production, as well as reverse logistics, as indicated on the CE model in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Circular economy model [6]

According to this model, previously produced products are returned after their consumption to secondary production. At the same time, the manufacturer is obliged to guarantee the restoration of the product or its disassembly into separate elements for secondary use.

Thereby, natural raw materials are not wasted again and energy is not wasted, in addition, the processing of materials does less harm to the environment, and the finished product produced from recycled materials has a lower cost.

As a result, the following are identified as the main objectives of the circular economy:

- 1) optimize the activities of economic entities through more appropriate methods of using resources;
- 2) organize a sustainable production cycle that allows more efficient use of existing production capacities;
- 3) ensure the pace of economic growth;
- 4) develop other economic directions (replenishment of natural resources, development of the labor market, etc.) [7].

At the second stage, we analyzed the experience of using the circular economy in the world at the present stage. At the same time, it should refer to the opinion of Klaus Schwab, an economist from Germany and president of the WEF in Davos, about the importance of a circular economy, since in the modern period the development of the economy as a whole is accelerating, and in a circular economy it becomes more predictable. In addition, in the West, Industry 4.0 (Fourth Industrial Revolution) is recognized as the basis for the transition to a circular, economy, since all aspects of human life and the functioning of production change with the spread of new technologies in the world (robotics, digitalization, artificial intelligence, the universal Internet). The mass introduction of the latest technologies has led to the realization of the importance of proper consumption and rational use of raw materials and energy, which reduces the anthropogenic impact on the environment.

This concept has found its distribution as part of the global strategy for sustainable development until

2030. It is described in a policy document adopted in 2015 by the UN (the main provisions are taken from the report "The Limits to Growth" by Dennis Meadows and co-authors, announced in the 80s of the last century). The UNO has identified the following ways to achieve global balance, arising from the principles of the circular economy: saving resources and optimizing energy, developing ecological methods of obtaining energy, introducing innovative technologies in all spheres of life, preserving the ecosystem, combating climate change and environmental degradation, ensuring rational production and consumption to reduce the volume of household landfills and waste, the consistency of all countries of the world in the planetary interests [8].

Analysis of foreign experience has shown that many countries prefer the circular economy as a new model of economic development. Countries adopt the concept of a closed cycle, both in general and in various areas of the economy, based on the priorities of socio-economic development. As a example, Germany introduced the concept of a circular economy one of the first, primarily in environmental policy. The United Kingdom and Denmark have introduced the principles of a circular economy in the field of waste management - in doing so, they want to create a zero-waste society in the country. The European Union in 2015 presented its action plan for the widespread introduction of the circular economy. This approach has accelerated the transition of EU countries to a circular economy. As a result, the following principle of the circular economy has been defined in the EU - following natural cycles through renewable energy sources.

The concept of a circular economy is being actively implemented in the Scandinavian countries.

Norway Government's ambition is to play a pioneering role in the development of a green, circular economy that makes better, more efficient use of resources. Norway will play this role by further developing policy and policy instruments both nationally and in cooperation with the EU, to develop a framework for value creation and green competitiveness in Norway. The strategy will underpin the Government's efforts to exploit the potential for value creation in Norwegian

business and industry more fully, with a more circular economy as the basis. It includes specific action points for the sectors that have been identified as having the greatest potential for circularity and green competitiveness in Norway: the bio-based sectors; the process industries; construction and buildings; and service industries, including retail and wholesale trade. [9].

Especially in Sweden, where the circular economy has become a national idea, supported not only by the state, but also by the people. So, for example, everyone can even hand over household waste such as batteries, light bulbs, small electronic gadgets, headphones, and so on in some Swedish supermarkets. The delivery of garbage is motivated in the form of a “deposit” system when buying a drink in a plastic, glass or aluminum bottle or can: the drink and packaging are paid separately. Upon return of the package, the deposit is returned, it can be spent in the same store or used in a charitable plan for the environment. In Sweden, from kindergarten, they begin to conduct environmental education and teach, for example, sorting garbage, making compost, and so on. For air travel in Sweden compensate for carbon dioxide emissions, and the proceeds are invested in the construction of wind or solar power plants. Taxes on non-green things (cars) and bonuses for eco-friendly things or actions (bicycles, scooters, walking) have been introduced in the country. In Sweden, literally everything is made from recycled waste: furniture, dishes, and so on.

In Scotland, there is a closed cycle in certain sectors of the economy, for example, in the textile sector, it is based on the “zero waste” principle. The government is interested in this approach and supports the achievement of similar goals, which are set for all waste in Scotland: to achieve 70% recycling by 2025 and a maximum of 5% waste disposal. The program was launched by the government on 9 June 2013 and is expected to generate £2.9 billion in potential savings through simple resource efficiency.

In China, the transition to a circular economy is also supported by the state, and this process is regulated by a special law. The result of this approach is the development of alternative energy in the country, both wind and solar. It should be noted that China was the first to use the concept of a circular economy when creating eco-industrial parks. Also in China, industrial projects are being actively implemented to create low-carbon cities, to introduce various kinds of nanotechnologies, and so on.

In South Korea, the circular economic system is included in the national economic development strategy of the country. At the same time, the economic development of the country is aimed at creating such branches of a closed economy as the creation of alternative engines and vehicles, the use of methods for the harmless processing of all types of waste, the purification of sea and fresh water, the development of state environmental projects and the active involvement of the population and business in them.

In Japan, they are actively and diversified fighting environmental pollution (water and air) within the framework of the circular economy, taking many measures to minimize methane emissions from farming

and waste processing. Japan has developed safe technologies for the utilization of methane and other harmful substances, for the manufacture of new materials while reducing the use of harmful substances in industrial production. It should also be noted the contribution of the Japanese government, which is implementing projects to protect the biosphere (on land and in the ocean) from black carbon and methane emissions. They also offer their technologies to other states - developing Asian countries [10].

The environmental benefits that countries are receiving from the circular economy are as follows: greenhouse gas emissions are reduced (halving from 2018 to 2030 is planned), soils are becoming healthier and more resilient (soil degradation costs about \$ 40 billion per year). The economic benefits are as follows: an increase in the potential for economic growth (increase in GDP), an increase in saved resources (up to 70%), an increase in employment (creation of new jobs). Thus, it is planned, for example, to create about 50 thousand jobs in the UK and 54 thousand new jobs in the Netherlands. Benefits of the circular economy for business: the emergence of new profit opportunities, reduced volatility and reliability of supply, increased demand for new services. These primarily include companies engaged in waste collection and reverse logistics, enterprises for the return to the system of end-of-life products, companies for the restoration of components, parts and finished products, companies that sell new products and digital sales platforms and some other.

At the third stage, an assessment was made of the documents of the concept of the circular economy developed in this area in Kazakhstan. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the concept of a circular economy has not been officially approved; some of its provisions were first disclosed in the concept of sustainable development until 2024. Then, in Kazakhstan, the concept of a green economy was developed, which notes such a task, based on the principles of a circular economy, as mitigating pressure on the environment. This concept states that by 2030-2050 the national economy of the country should switch to the use of natural resources on the basis of sustainability and renewability [11].

In the Strategy for achieving carbon neutrality until 2060, which was developed in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the circular economy is one of the principles for its implementation and is as follows: a circular economy is an economy based on reducing consumption and using secondary resources. Other principles include phased implementation, openness and public interaction, and balance. Sectoral low-carbon development based on the closed cycle economy is directed to Kazakhstan in such sectors as energy, industry, agriculture and forestry, waste management. A fair transition to a new form of economy, support for green investments, the formation of a new public consciousness, and so on are defined as cross-cutting approaches to such development [12].

Based on the above strategy, the basic principles of the circular economy in energy, industry, agriculture and forestry and waste management are involved in Kazakhstan. There is a gradual transition to a circular

economy.

The transition to a circular economy in the Republic of Kazakhstan is designed to solve such important and existing problems in the country as:

- 1) processing of industrial waste and their reuse (such waste is mainly emitted by mining enterprises);
- 2) processing of collected household waste or their environmental disposal (household waste of the population and certain types of enterprises);
- 3) purification of water resources and their reuse (resources of water-deficient regions of the country).

According to statistics, in Kazakhstan, the processing of industrial and household waste is growing, but has insignificant volumes. Thus, over the past five years, about 15-18% of 4 million tons of waste has been processed MSW (municipal solid waste) in the country, and the share of industrial waste disposal and processing is slightly higher - more than 30% (there is no division of processing and disposal). These are very low index compared to Western countries. The greatest activity in this direction can be traced in the cities of Almaty and Astana and in regional centers, it is differentiated unevenly and across the regions of the country. In Kazakhstan, the number of companies dealing with MSW is growing, but they are still few. There are no statistical calculations on the level of MSW processing and the inclusion of industrial and other enterprises in the circular economy. The main sectoral types of waste circulation in Kazakhstan are enterprises for the processing of paper, polyethylene glass and food waste. The least developed enterprises in Kazakhstan are processing textiles, non-ferrous metal scrap and wood. There are facilities that specialize in the recycling of batteries, automotive components, tires and used oils. Enterprises for the processing of waste electronic and electrical equipment are developing [13; 14].

Thereby, we have considered the main concepts of the circular economy and foreign experience. The main strategic documents, according to which a circular economy is developing in Kazakhstan, and some statistical data have been studied. It has been established that in Kazakhstan so far only a transition to a closed cycle economy is taking place. It is recommended in Kazakhstan to use the experience of European countries, which at the national level have included the principles of a circular economy in their strategic documents for sustainable development, have created special funds and effective platforms. The Japanese experience also deserves special attention, as a resource-constrained country was able to transition to a highly efficient closed economy through a law passed in 2000 to promote the efficient use of resources. This approach has allowed Japanese businesses to recycle up to 98% of their used metal waste and 90% of their old electronics waste. As a result, almost all materials used in Japan are returned for recycling and remanufacturing.

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